

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.
How will **DATAMITE** benefit society? Who is behind the project? Enjoy
your reading!

Jordi Arjona Aroca, DATAMITE's Coordinator

**In DATAMITE we
invite you to make
some puzzles!**

Welcome! We invite you to make some puzzles!

Data is nothing but pieces of information that we put together like a puzzle to extract something valuable like a model or a forecast. Making that puzzle is already complicated... but what if the pieces are wrong?
This is the reality for many organizations and their data.

**Read the full article by
Jordi Arjona, the Project
Coordinator**

Who is behind DATAMITE?

DATAMITE is a 3-year-project funded by the **European Commission** under the **Horizon Europe** research and innovation programme. Led by [Instituto Tecnológico de Informatica \(ITI\)](#), and composed of **26 partners from 12 countries**, our consortium comprises a balanced team of complementary organisations, including research & development partners, academic partners, large industrial partners, SMEs, and a standardisation body.

[Discover more about our team and our Kick-off meeting](#)

How will DATAMITE benefit society?

DATAMITE supports open source

DATAMITE has data sharing in its DNA! We develop a **modular open-source framework targeted at organisations of any size**, letting them to focus on maximising their compatibility and ease of integration with any system already in place. In addition, we produce high quality training material supporting a strong

DATAMITE contributes to the European Year of skills

2023 is the **European Year of Skills**, which aims to help companies, in particular small and medium enterprises (SMEs), to address skills shortages in the EU. **DATAMITE**, well aware of the need to improve society digital skills, will contribute to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple

open-source community that supports newcomers.

open-source training materials the project will generate.

Discover
where to find
our open-
source

Learn more
about our
role in the
EU's Year of

DATAMITE #WomenInScience

Introducing Daniela Greven, leader of DATAMITE's Work Package 4

In **DATAMITE** we celebrate and value the work of all the women who have decided to dedicate their path to **STEM**. On the occasion of the **International Day of women and Girls in Science** (11th February), we talk to **Daniela Greven**, member of **DATAMITE** on behalf of [FIR an der RWTH Aachen](#), and leader of the Work Package 4.

Meet Daniela Greven

Creating synergies

Project cluster: AI, Data and Robotics Partnership Projects

DATAMITE exploits the leading position of the consortium to nurture strategic synergies, creating visibility and fostering adoption of the open-source modules among the major EU ecosystems. Special attention to build technical and promotional synergies with the project cluster under the same topic: [HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-04: Technologies and solutions for data trading, monetizing, exchange and interoperability \(AI, Data and Robotics Partnership\)](#)

[Discover the project cluster](#)

**Funded by
the European Union**

You've received it because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

This newsletter has been prepared by the DATAMITE project. It does not reflect the opinion of any single DATAMITE partner. The DATAMITE project and its consortium partners are not liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of this publication.

[View in browser](#) | [Unsubscribe](#)

